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Mental health research: misalignment between priorities and needs in the face of shifting societal demands¹

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Introduction

This paper describes a study that aims to produce a comprehensive and inclusive mapping of Mental Health (MH) research for informing strategic planning by public funding agencies. In short, it aims to map and provide information on current research in mental health to inform and help funding agencies reflect on their research and innovation priorities (Pielke and Sarewitz, 2007; Wallace and Rafols, 2015). The emphasis lies in spotting misalignments and gaps of current research efforts against perceived societal needs and demands in light of shifting mental health needs (Christensen et al., 2013; Marmott, 2020).

A primary motivation for developing a more comprehensive mapping is the observation that current health research and innovation is framed in primarily biomedical or clinical terms (the only previous bibliometric study by Larivière and Grant (2017) was framed thus). Given the context of the global COVID-19 pandemic occurring in the backdrop of this study, it has become apparent that disease is not merely a medical phenomenon; it is interwoven with social, political, economic, among other factors. Despite this, the dominance of a medical framing persists, even within MH research. Consequently, there is a tendency to prioritize research that is either fundamental or aimed at therapeutic approaches to address acute health crises.

Given ongoing debates towards more systemic understandings of health, it is necessary to shift toward a mapping of health that takes into account a broader view and includes a more diverse set of research topics and innovation actors. This requires considering prevention, rehabilitation, healthcare services, and socioeconomic determinants of health as central in the future of mental health research.

¹ This short paper is based and draws directly on a [report](#) and [blog posts](#) of a project supported by Vinnova (Swedish Innovation Agency) and CWTS, Leiden University.

The study has three objectives:

- to portray the views of stakeholders on research priorities. This includes their views on the balance between research areas, and how and why future investments should depart from current activities.
- to produce and characterize a broad map of mental health research,
- to describe research activities across countries and organisations in particular subfields,

In summary, the overall motivation of the project is to produce and test a methodology that combines analytical tools with expert consultation methods in order to inform and help funding agencies reflect on research and innovation priorities, with an emphasis in spotting gaps and misalignments with perceived societal needs and demands.

Approach, data and methods

Mapping publications related to MH is challenging. First, because the definitions of MH and well-being are contested. Second, because it is an issue that spans disparate disciplines, each of them with different understandings of mental health. And third, because mental disorders can be the second or third topic in a project, given that it is constitutive with many other health and wellbeing concerns or biological processes: for example, social identity among ethnic minorities is related to psychological stress ([cluster 1536 in map](#)); protein folding to Alzheimer ([c795](#)); sexual orientation to social stigma and depression ([c859](#)) and the financial crisis to suicide ([c2624](#)). Given these challenges, we developed the bibliometric mapping in parallel to qualitative interviews and focus groups that were used to contextualise and triangulate insights.

Given the diversity of understandings, we report the views of stakeholders, both in academia and practice, on what MH research is or should be. Building on three focus groups and several interviews, we later present insights on what stakeholders perceive to be the current research foci, and what they believe are actual research priorities against what they see as most needed research directions, which tend to point to areas beyond the traditional areas of psychiatry, clinical psychology and clinical neurology.

Second, we conduct high-level statistical analysis based on conventional medical terms and disciplinary categories on the distribution of publications across disorders, countries, organisations and funders. However, given the contested boundaries of MH and the goal to capture research topics outside mainstream (bio)medical disciplines, we complement the conventional statistical approach with an exploratory mapping.

Third, we introduce an inclusive research landscape with the aim of providing the readers comprehensive information on publication clusters related to MH and well-being, although some of the topics may be seen as remote to MH. We start this map with the publications tagged by Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) related to MH by the US National Library of Medicine. These publications are located in clusters of related publications within a cognitive map based on article-level clusters. The purpose of the research landscape is to facilitate the exploration by stakeholders of research topics beyond our initial core. For each cluster, detailed information on the contents and the main countries and organisations is provided.

Next, we show how the research landscape allows for the exploration of the ‘portfolio’, i.e., the distribution of publications over the clusters of specific countries, selected organisations, and funders. With these portfolios we can compare the issues that are being most supported by institutional research against the stated policy priorities or perceived needs of stakeholders and users. A dedicated [website](#) provides interactive access to the research landscape of mental health and the portfolios.

Two key methodological choices need to be taken into account. First, following conventional classifications (WHO’s and PubMed’s), we have not explicitly included neurological disorders, except for dementia. Second, publication clusters are based on citation flows, and thus reflect a particular view of research dynamics. Publications can be grouped in many other meaningful ways providing contrasting views of the same data. Against our initial hopes, this citation perspective has not proved very useful to make clear distinctions between different goals of research in terms of treatment, prevention, rehabilitation, etcetera. Instead, our clusters reflect research topics.

Qualitative findings: perceptions on shifting societal needs and demands

We conducted qualitative interviews and focus groups in parallel to the bibliometric mapping. This is important in order for the mapping to try to address the issues raised. These were the main insights:

The gap between research and practice and a demand for implementation research

Experts and social workers interviewed express frequently that there is a gap between the scientific communities and the communities of professionals working on mental health issues. This gap makes it difficult to adopt the results of the research, since in most fields (with the exception of highly specialized medicine), the implementation of the results from the reading of academic publications is considered unrealistic. The health professionals interviewed emphasize the need for more intervention-oriented and implementation-oriented research, especially in the context of public health research.

Growing prevention needs and demands

Society’s mental health needs and demands are changing, and so are the ways in which research, as well as mental health services, is conducted. Experts interviewed point out that there is a growing awareness of mental health issues, which has led to more demand for prevention and rehabilitation, and to address subclinical mental discomfort (which could be increasing), which means will and need. to care for people who experience mental illness before they can be considered ill. This emphasis on the prevention, rehabilitation, and reduction of social and environmental stressors would require the transfer of mental health care (and research) tasks from clinical settings to non-clinical settings, such as schools, the family or jobs.

Research on shared tasks requires plural and transdisciplinary approaches

In the face of demands for the prevention of discomfort and the promotion of well-being, experts point out that the standardized and medical mental health research model addressed in clinical settings is not sufficient. Knowledge associated with multiple disciplines such as education, occupational psychology, urban planning, social work, the environment, and information and communication technologies needs to be mobilized, researching the social

and environmental contexts that influence mental health. For example, with mental health experts co-researching and supporting teachers and nurses. Promoting well-being as a ‘shared task’ between multiple disciplines and various social sectors (school, family, work, etc.) requires a broad, diverse and transdisciplinary approach to mental health.

Presentation of analysis via an interactive visualisation

Since this study is aimed for a policy audience with the broad variety of stakeholders relevant in MH, we documented the current distribution of research for mental health across disciplines and topics using publication data (Web of Science) with an [interactive visualization interface](#)ⁱ that allows users to compare research efforts by specific countries, organizations and funders thus facilitating the exploration and benchmarking of MH research according to users’ interests.

1. The *Publication output* visualisation allows to compare the number of publication of territories, organisations, and funders.
2. The *Disciplinary profiles* visualisation aims to provide a first perspective of the distribution across disciplines of territories, organisations, and funders. Disciplines are aggregates of Web of Science (WoS) Categories based on similar citation patterns.

Figure 1: Disciplinary profiles in mental health research.

3. The *Research landscape* visualisation guides the user to a more in-depth analysis by showing the science map of the 280 publication clusters that are most related to MH. Clusters are CWTS article-level-clusters. This map is aimed at supporting the exploration of the epistemic space of mental health.

The map has a triangular structure that helps users think about research options in mental health. Psychiatry lies at the middle of the triangle. At the left-hand side there are psychology-related clusters, with social psychology at the bottom left and experimental psychology at the middle-top. Neuroscience lie at the right-hand side of the triangle, with neuroimaging at the middle-top and biochemistry and molecular biology at the

bottomright. The bottom side of the triangle goes from public health to basic biomedical research. The horizontal axis is related to more social sciences approaches (left) to more clusters related to psychosocial interventions and healthcare systems (middle-left) to clinical psychopharmacological research in mental disorder (middle-right) to neurosciences and neurology (right).

Understanding this structure is important in order to interpret the The tab on the top righthand side allows to visualise the distribution over the clusters of disciplines, of disorders and the cluster characteristics, such as growth, publications authored by companies or hospitals, and mentions in patents, news, or policy documents.

Figure 2: Research landscape of mental health.

4. The *Portfolios* visualisation describes the distribution of publications by countries, organisations, and funders over the 280 clusters of the research landscape, as well as their relative specialisation (i.e., whether they publish more than expected) in the cluster. Critically, it allows comparison between units, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Research portfolios of mental health for the Spanish (top) and Swedish (bottom) Health Research Councils.

The interactive visualisation is presented for about 50 countries, 50 organisations and 50 funders that are among the most active in MH, with a focus on facilitating comparison directly with users who have in-depth knowledge of MH.

Main new insights in relation to mapping methodology

Lack of a good classification system to allocate publications to health approaches such as prevention, treatment or diagnoses

Neither current available bibliometric categorisation tools such as MeSH or Web of Science Categories, nor article-level clusters (e.g. as used in CWTS or Elsevier's SciVal) provide a classification that can clearly allocate publications into the type of areas health categories most relevant of the purpose of this study as requested by Vinnova, namely to distinguish research about social determinants, prevention, rehabilitation, treatment, health systems, diagnosis, etcetera. MeSH categories prevention or diagnosis, proved to be too narrowly medical and not useful for this study.

In article-level clusters research topics related to therapeutics or diagnostics are more associated with specific mental disorders and are more easily identifiable when trying to set research priorities according to conventional classification methods. Research topics related to healthcare systems and the social determinants of mental health concern more general mental health benefits. The policy implication is that the specific framing used in classifications of research funding is likely to favour research on different types of mental health interventions.

We have based our interpretation on associations of disciplinary and clusters with certain approaches: thus social sciences are assumed to do research on social determinant, clinical disciplines on treatment. Also an article-level cluster on refugees and depression is associated with social determinants, a cluster on psychiatry and schizophrenia is associated with treatment. This allows to make interpretations that lead (hopefully!) to useful insights, as illustrated in Figure 4 in the case of Alzheimer. However, not all disorders show clear patterns.

In summary, we would like to highlight that the classification of publications into categories across different health research approached remains a serious challenge for bibliometrics.

Figure 4. Position of Alzheimer-related research in the landscape of mental health. The cluster on the left is related to healthcare, the cluster of middle to psychiatric treatment and the cluster at the right related to biochemistry of Alzheimer-related proteins.

Towards a plural and tentative of the research landscape of mental health

The mapping of mental health is ambiguous given the multiple interpretations of mental health. To accommodate this plurality, we have aimed at developing a comprehensive and inclusive research landscape of mental health, that would include topics which are relatively small currently, but that some stakeholders would like to further support in the future.

For this purpose, we have included in the research landscape (as shown in Figure 2) all the article-level clusters that had more than 20% of publications tagged as related to MH. The size of the clusters shows the number of publications, while the colours of the clusters show the percentage of publications related to MH (blue means low percentage, brown high percentage). In using this technique, we see that, in accordance with stakeholders divergent views, MH cannot be neatly delineated. This scheme thus allows to show that some areas with low percentage according to MeSH definition could be very important to some stakeholders – for example, clusters on telemedicine ([c1613](#)), or sedentary life ([c93](#)) would not be visible.

The coloring from blue to brown thus provides gradient information about the degree to which different parts of the research landscape *might be* related to mental health, rather than

providing a single and definitive delineation. While technically, the approach we propose is not new, we believe we are making a conceptual contribution by showing that the map is a gradient of degree of potential MH relatedness.

Substantive quantitative findings on Mental Health portfolios

As shown in Figure 1, psychiatry-related disciplines, neurosciences, and biomedicine constitute the largest share of research, with around 60%-75% of all research. It also confirms experts' perceptions that there is relatively little mental health research in social science, public health and policy, and in healthcare systems, with around 10-20% of publications altogether. According to stakeholders, this low percentage is due to the relative lack of academic prestige of qualitative and implementation research among health funders and evaluation systems. However, Figure 1 also shows that Sweden (and the Nordic countries if you explore the interactive visualisation) has a more balanced portfolio than countries such as Germany or the UK.

The portfolio visualization then allows us to see in detail the specialization of specific units. For example (as shown in Figure 5) that Sweden is specialised in several topics related to prevention and healthcare research such as community treatment, and various social determinants of mental health, including inequalities, job satisfaction or insecurity, and immigration or refugees. For example, within the identified cluster of research on community treatment, a detailed case study revealed that research from diverse disciplinary departments, such as one working on social work, are central to this research.

Figure 5. Sweden's portfolio in the research landscape of mental health.

Concluding remarks

While we had previous experiences of using portfolio mapping to discuss research priorities (e.g. Ciarli and Rafols, 2019), this is the first time that we have applied this mixed method methodology in the context of a specific policy need – in this case, the request by Vinnova to explore and compare research on prevention, rehabilitation and social determinants of mental health.

Since we found serious challenges in terms of selection and classification of publication into relevant categories, we have used multiple visualisations in terms of disciplinary profile and topic article-level clusters. Triangulating evidence with these multiple mappings, the analysis supports the view of many stakeholders that there is relatively low level of research in prevention, social determinants, health care systems and that more research on these issues.

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ⁱ The website is available here:

<https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/tim5920/viz/MentalHealthtool/MHtool>